

ADOPTION OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE WORDS INTO THE KARLUK DIALECTS OF THE SAMARKAND REGION

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Abstract:

This article reveals the specific features of Uzbek dialects belonging to the Karluk dialects of the city and region of Samarkand. Also, the occurrence of loanwords in these dialects, their pronunciation, and spelling are analyzed using examples. Comments are made on the topic. The work carried out in this area is also discussed.

Key words: Karluk dialects, Samarkand city, Samarkand region, Uzbek dialects, lexical-semantic group, loanwords, pronunciation, spelling.

It is known that, like any language, loanwords occupy a special place in the vocabulary of a dialect. No language and its underlying dialect can develop in isolation from other languages. In this regard, the famous orientalist Ansariddin Ibrohimov, in his doctoral dissertation "Indian Words in the Boburnoma", expresses the following important points: "... any language, as a rule, consists of the addition of various lexical elements" [A.P. Barannikov]. "The mutual influence of languages, as a rule, has led and will lead to their mutual enrichment" [I.U. Asfandiyorov]. "... a pure language in the world, in which not a single word from other languages has not been and cannot be" [Ibrohimov A,2002].

It is clear from this information that the dialects, which are the living spoken language of the people, have also been enriched by the adoption of words from various languages.

It is known that the Uzbek and Tajik nations have been in a very friendly and harmonious relationship for a very long time, so the Uzbek language has adopted many words from the Tajik language. We can also know this from the following thoughts of Karim Shoniyozov: "The fact that the Turkic, Sogdian and Tajik groups speak both languages has arisen as a result of their centuries-long living in the same territory and continuous economic and cultural ties with each other. It is also worth noting that no matter what state, ethnic or tribal association these two peoples (Uzbek and Tajik) were on the territory of, they have always lived in harmony, there have been no wars of extermination between them" [Шонийзов К,2001].

Representatives of the karluk dialect mainly include urban and urban-type dialects and dialects [Ashirboyev S,2021]. We also tried to study the lexical features of Uzbek dialects specific to the Qarluq dialect of Samarkand. A significant part of the vocabulary of the karluk dialect of Samarkand is made up of general Turkic words. Words in this dialect are mainly borrowed from three sources: Persian (Tajik), Arabic, and Russian, but there are also words that have come from other languages, although to a lesser extent.

In particular, as S. Ashirbayev rightly noted: "The results of scientific research show that the dialects have more Persian (Tajik) words in their vocabulary, less Arabic words, and very few Russian-international words, which indicates that the process of assimilation of foreign words takes more time" [Ashirboyev S,2021].

It is known that the lexicon of the Karluk dialects of the Samarkand region is distinguished by its diversity and originality. After all, the ethnic composition of the city's population is diverse, and they communicate mainly in the Karluk dialect, partly in the Oghuz dialect. It is noteworthy that, although scientific work has been carried out on the Kipchak and Oghuz dialects in the Samarkand region to date, there has been almost no extensive monographic linguistic research on the lexicon of our object of study [Tillabayeva Z,2022].

It should be noted that "... language elements are formed in the communicative process not only depending on the community, group, strata entering into communication, the representatives of which people they consist of, but also on the situation and sphere of communication. Each community has its own style of speech, habits, and ways of using language units. From this point of view, they (socium) differ from each other and acquire sociolinguistic significance" [Курбаниязов Г.А,2021]. Therefore, as in other languages and dialects, the historical interaction of the people speaking the Uzbek language with Turkic and non-Turkic peoples leads to the diversity of Uzbek dialects. It can be seen that the dialects of the region we are studying, along with common Turkic words, contain a large number of loanwords from Arabic, Persian-Tajik, Russian and other European languages.

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It can be rightly said that, as E. Begmatov wrote, "... the examination of the lexicon from a historical-etymological point of view is focused on two issues: a) determining the native words in the Uzbek lexicon; b) determining the borrowed words in the Uzbek lexicon. On this basis, the words in the Uzbek lexicon can be divided into two large layers from a historical-etymological point of view: 1. Native layer in the Uzbek lexicon. 2. Acquired layer in the Uzbek lexicon" [Бегматов Э, 1985]. We also found it necessary to study the materials collected during our research into 2 groups, relying on this theory.

It is natural that there is a large use of borrowed words in the vocabulary of Uzbek dialects. It should be noted that "... there is no language itself, isolated from the influence of other languages and enclosed in a certain shell" [Гулямова Н, 1975].

Linguist Sh. Shoabdurahmonov emphasizes the diversity of the lexical layer of dialects belonging to the Uzbek literary language, explaining the presence of lexical units related to Arabic, Tajik, Russian and other languages [Шаабдурахманов Ш, 1983].

Indeed, the dialects of the studied region have a large number of loanwords in their vocabulary, which serve to ensure the diversity and uniqueness of this dialect.

It should be recognized that the Russian language is one of the main external sources that nourishes not only the lexicon of Uzbek dialects, but also the speech of the population living in the city of Samarkand. Many large and small linguistic works have been created on this issue. In particular, it should be emphasized that many scientific works have been created in this regard by A.K. Borovkov, B. Reshetov, Sh. Shoabdurahmonov, M. Mirzayev, F. Abdullayev, O. Usmonov, E. Fozilov, M. Pulatov, I. Rasulov, F. Kamolov and other scientists. Dialectologist N. Murodova also classifies the words that passed from Russian and European languages into the Uzbek language and its dialects into thematic groups. It is especially emphasized that these units undergo various phonetic changes in the speech of dialect representatives [Муродова Н, 2019].

In our opinion, this idea is justified, and Russian words have their synonyms in the Karluk dialect of Samarkand. We can find such units in many areas of activity.

We would also like to give some of our considerations directly related to this issue. We have witnessed the use of Russian words in the lexicon of the Karluk dialects of Samarkand region in the following ways:

1) without any changes, it is used exactly: škäf (closet), dām (roof), vännä (bath), kånälizätsijä (sewer), sänätārij (sanatorium), etc.

2) it is pronounced with a phonetic change:

- when expressing names of equipment: māšin (car), aftābus (bus), trāmbāj (tram), tilpān (telephone), tilbizār (television), ustāl (table-chair), pājiz (train), mātor (motor), etc.

- titles and professions: such as mili:sä (police), präkrār (prosecutor), bugalti:r (accountant), dukhti:r (doctor), direkti:r (director), süd (judge), fermir (farmer), mäntor (fitter), präfesir (professor), dätsen (associate professor).

- names of state institutions: detsät (detsky sad), intirnät (boarding school), zävät (factory), dāmātdix (dom otdykha), letsij (lyceum), etc.

- names of clothes and shoes: bürük (trousers), kästüm (suit), pätkä (boots), käloč (galoshy), žimpir (jumper), pältä (coat), kerzävāj (boots), šarti (shorty), etc.

- names of food products: boličkä (bun), pičini (biscuit), väflik (waffle), präjnik (pryaniki), bolkä (loaf), märāžni (mороgenoe), kifir (kefir), etc.

- household items: loškä (stove), skävärätka (pan), duxāfkä (oven), piltä (stove), xälādelnik (refrigerator), mikrāvālnāfkä (microwave oven), etc.

- names of houses and their parts: čirdäk (attic), verän (porch), kälidār (corridor), bälkän (balcony), kukhni (kitchen), etc.

- when expressing different concepts: äbreskä (obrezka), pädärkä (podarka), ätdix (otdyx), prävä (voditelskoe pravo), zinäk (sign), nümür (number), päviskä (story), ispräfkä (document), etc.

3) as a basic morpheme, it is used in compound words: tabelchi (accountant), shafirlik (driver), mashinachi (seamstress), milisakhana (police court), nelug varaq (tax receipt), kastumposh (intellectual), papuruskash (smoker), gazitkhan (educated), majliskhana (meeting place), darskhana (classroom), dzileti (teaching), shajiri (poetry), sinifkhana (classroom), etc.

4) is used in colloquial meanings by forming a word combination: krišäsi ketkän/ psikh ädäm (mentally ill person), ispräfkäsi bar buni (mentally ill person), tak urgändäj bolli (unexpected mental shock), peškä bollim-kallim (to become an insignificant person), mengä pädärkä bolli (a calamity befell me), pävestkäsi kelli (used in reference to someone who was close to death), and so on. Some of their Uzbek equivalents are also used in parallel: "I have lost my mind/psych adēm - I have lost my mind, "I have become a father to me" - "I have become a slave to me", "I have become a slave to me" - "I have become a slave to me" and so on.

Thus, in the lexicon of the Karluk dialects of the Samarkand region, words that have entered from Russian and other languages through Russian, unlike other dialects, are used in various spheres of social life and reflect the political, economic, technical and cultural changes that have occurred. They are actively used in dialectal speech, serving to express the subjective and stylistic features of speech.

Nowadays, the rapid development of science and technology has led to the introduction of many new neologisms into our language. Previously, words from European languages were absorbed into our language through Russian, but later they were absorbed directly: fax (fax), internet (internet), computer (computer), interview (interview), marketing (marketing), currency (currency), etc. N. Komlev noted that currently the number of words related to computers and their technology in the Uzbek language is more than three hundred words [Комлев Н. Г., 1995].

As Samikhon Ashirbayev emphasizes: "All dialects participate to one degree or another in the formation of the Uzbek literary language. The Uzbek literary language takes lexical, phonetic, and grammatical features from a specific dialect and dialect group as a fact of the literary language and develops along with the development of that dialect and dialect group, because dialects are living languages, they are constantly developing and changing, and due to this, the literary language also develops." [Ashirboyev S, 2021].

During our observation, we witnessed that the bilingual and trilingual characteristics of the speech of the population of the city and region of Samarkand are determined by socio-cultural processes, the existence of close communication between dialects and languages.

"In scientific research, the modern lexical layers of Uzbek dialects have been studied. There is almost a similarity in the naming of the layers in them, but there are also certain differences in their composition, depending on the profession of the representatives of the dialect, the influence of related Turkic and non-Turkic languages, and the approach to studying the lexicon of the dialect" [Ashirboyev S, 2021]. For this reason, in order to draw certain conclusions about the characteristics of the lexical layers of this dialect, we analyzed the lexical properties of some borrowed words in the dialect.

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